

AN INVESTIGATION OF ENGLISH AS FOREIGN LANGUAGE STUDENTS' ATTITUDES TOWARD IMPROVING THEIR SPEAKING ABILITIES AT KRI UNIVERSITIES

Zubair Hamad Muhi¹, Innocent Nasuk Dajang^{2*}

Urmia University, Urmia, West Azarbaijan Province, Iran¹

University of Jos, Jos, Plateau State, Nigeria²

*Corresponding author email: djangi@unijos.edu.ng

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ABSTRACT

The study examines English as Foreign Language (EFL) students' attitude towards developing their speaking abilities at KRI University in order to better understand the disparities in speaking competency among undergraduates. The study utilized a quantitative approach and employed a 4-item interview survey to gather data for the study. The survey interview questionnaire was adopted from Wang, Kim, Bong, and Ahan (2013) and administered to 100 students in the departments of English of six universities in Iraq's Kurdistan Region. A semi-structured interview was developed for EFL students. The questionnaire was online and an open-ended one. The data from the participants was analyzed using thematic analysis with (SPSS) software. The finding revealed a perceived failure in EFL students' English-speaking skills, and this was reported along with causes of the perceived difficulty. The finding also revealed a poor level of speaking ability among EFL undergraduates as well as little education in the skill at the university level. Apart from these, the study discovered some major challenges for EFL students such as lack of confidence, lack of planning, a demotivating atmosphere, incorrect word choice, poor gestures, and incorrect style which made the students not to be successful in their speaking abilities. The study suggested that EFL learners' competency should be securitized to strengthen their speaking abilities in the light of the results of the study. Speaking is a crucial ability in language acquisition and EFL teachers should help their students acquire it. As a means of improving students' communicative ability, task-based instruction should be utilized in educational institutions and universities. The implication of this paper is that speaking difficulties among EFL students in the Iraqi Kurdistan Region institution can be solved by putting greater focus on this ability. There are several issues to consider, including teachers, instructional methodologies, the curriculum, extracurricular activities, and assessment rules.

Keywords: EFL students, KRI, speaking proficiency, semi-structured interview thematic analysis

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INTRODUCTION

Speaking is a significant skill that English as foreign language learners' programs have strived to promote by seeking to enhance speaking abilities so that students can communicate and express themselves correctly. It is now possible to learn a language and speak it fluently (Glover, 2011). Speaking is seen to be the most difficult talent to learn especially due to its spontaneity and the adoption of conventional teaching methods that place emphasis on memory and students' passive involvement (Shabani, 2013). Contrarily, studies have indicated that improving speaking ability requires students' active involvement in the learning process as well as a motivating environment.

Given the significance of speaking ability, several English teachers focus on how to teach speaking in their lessons in an engaging way. For English language learners, mastering speaking is challenging since it takes a lot of work. You cannot prepare specific words or sentences before speaking. Speaking happens in real time, unlike reading or writing; often, the person we are speaking with is waiting for us to say something. What you wish to say cannot be edited or revised by us (Anderson & Nunan, 2003). It is all about managing the discussion and speaking spontaneously when it comes to speaking. Fauzan (2014) states that oral communication includes two or more persons negotiating meanings, and it is always contextualized (O'Malley & Pearce, 1996 & Nunan, 1999). One of the most challenging components of learning English for English learners is the capacity to interact spontaneously, negotiate meanings, manage a conversation, according to Efrizal (2012) Pourhosein Gilakjani (2016),

What is more, speaking has always been regarded as the most important ability to acquire throughout the history of studying and teaching foreign languages for a variety of reasons. First off, conferences and research studies on language instruction have traditionally concentrated on techniques and methods for teaching speaking. Secondly, a massive number of books, audios, and videos for conversation and other speaking courses are constantly being produced. Additionally, a lot of language learners believe that speaking fluently is the best indicator of language proficiency. Instead of the capability to read, write, or understand oral language, they define fluency as the ability to talk with others. They consider speaking to be the most important skill they can master. The need for English-speaking proficiency has significantly increased in recent years due to the language's rising status as a global language, or lingua franca. It is used as a working language by 85% of international corporations (Crystal, 1997). Many people all over the world have chosen to learn English as a second language (ESL) or as a foreign language (EFL) in order to be able to speak it. According to Graves (2008), "the goals of learning a language in TL-removed situations are many, but the priority is to study language for communication, to improve one's chances at employment, to broaden one's horizons both literally and figuratively, to be a global citizen" (p. 156).

Speaking skills are prioritized in society, which is reflected in the tendency to judge English proficiency by one's ability to talk. In fact, a lot of pupils think that speaking and listening skills are more important than reading and writing skills. According to them, speaking is the most important language skill to learn, and mastering speaking abilities is how they evaluate learning accomplishment (Burnkart, 1998).

Theoretical framework

Effective communication may be a particularly important opportunity to develop language and social skills. The study adopts a psycholinguistic theory as its framework. Darjowijojo (2005) argues that people do not necessarily view the use of language as very difficult. Language usage can successfully be easily achieved because they are repeatedly done as a habit. Babies learn by imitation despite not having any idea of what they are imitating. Such imitations grow from single words to phrases and sentences. Learners should often listen from native speaker speech by tape recorder, videos, or other means and then practice it. The goal of imitation is not to focus on the meaningful interaction, but for focusing on some particular element of language form. Brown (2007) affirmed that given an opportunity to learners to listen and to orally repeat certain strings of language that may pose some linguistic difficulty either phonological or grammatical can help them perform better. This theory is in line with the aim of this paper geared towards not just identifying challenges of learners but also considering ways of improvement in their speaking abilities.

Literature Review

Many studies have examined the problems and difficulties that EFL students have when taking part in speaking activities in the classroom; prominent studies include those by Zhang and Liu (2008), Gan (2012), Al Hosni (2014), Wang (2014), and Vietnam (2015). Their main focus was on college students learning English in settings where many of them do not know the language. In these researches, speech difficulties among students were discussed in relation to academic achievement. For instance, Zhang and Liu (2008) examined the personality traits, self-esteem, and anxiety related to learning a foreign language in Chinese EFL students. These issues result in a wide range of other issues, including inhibition caused by students' fear of making mistakes, anxiety, personality traits, self-esteem, and an unsecure atmosphere for communication outside of the classroom. The results of previous studies on the difficulties faced by EFL students in learning the language call for more effort towards language learning among the learners. Many EFL students still struggle to grasp the ability of speaking, despite the fact that several studies have been conducted to help learners. Another reason would be that the bulk of these research concentrated on linguistic aspects of second language learning, which is thought to be "the most complicated and difficult ability to acquire" (Hinkel, 2005).

Speaking is so prominent in our daily language use that it contributes to this complexity. In other words, because speech is so intertwined with everyday interactions, it is hard to define. Numerous academic disciplines, including linguistics, psychology, anthropology, and sociology have also had an impact on speaking. (Gumperz, 1999)

Speaking is a multi-sensory activity because it includes paralinguistic components such as eye contact, facial expressions of emotion, body language, tempo, pauses, changes in voice quality, and pitch modulation (Thornbury, 2005). The way an individual speaks seems to be heavily influenced by culture, which has implications for how English is taught and learned. A "linguistic repertory" often repeated phrases are also developed by native speakers since speaking is fundamentally unexpected (Gumperz, cited in Yorio, 1980). This helps to provide a diversity of speech. It would be beneficial to emphasize these conventions, practices, and linguistic components in a speaking lesson while instructing speaking. Speaking is referred to as a kind of verbal communication utilized mostly for interpersonal and business-related goals (Nunan, 1999). Speaking is also extremely interactive and social since it occurs most frequently when two persons are face-to-face (Van Lier, 1989). To suggest that "face-to-face communication" is not the only way to have a conversation.

Naturally, the purpose of speaking instruction is to improve students' speech production. As a result, language training in the classroom should aim to maximize each student's use of the language (Haozhang, 1997). Speaking is one of the most crucial and required talents that must be regularly practiced in order to communicate verbally, according to Febriyanti (2011). Speaking is a skill that many ESL and EFL students prioritize highly. The fluency of a language is a common way for learners to gauge their progress in learning it. According to Zaremba (2006), speaking appears to be the most significant of the four macro-English abilities for communication. Furthermore, according to Sayed (2005), first-year students in Egypt have difficulty with oral communication with others, preventing them from utilizing English for communicative purposes. As a result, the primary aim for teachers and students is to be able to interact successfully in spoken English with native English speakers.

Gaps in the Literature

The review of these articles identifies concerns with speaking abilities in order to improve other languages, which also aids EFL learners in speaking. It may also have a lot of inhibitions that arrive before the university students' speaking periods. This study tries to dig further into these hurdles and aims to obtain information and encourage students to improve their speaking abilities, which are more important than other skills. This study tries to fill in the gaps in our knowledge.

Objectives

For self-regulated content from this paper, there are two types of objectives that have been categorized:

1. To identify the causes for developing EFL students' speaking abilities at KRG institutions.
2. To encourage student-to-student interaction and cooperative learning by creating groups and boost speaking proficiency.

METHODOLOGY

The instrument in this study was developed through an open-ended questionnaire. The method used in this study was quantitative. In six institutions, four semi-structured interviews were conducted. The interviews aimed to learn more about teachers' and students' perceptions of the elements that hinder students' ability to communicate in English. All of the interviews were taped, and transcribed for analysis

Descriptive Statistics

It reveals that 25% respondents were from Duhok University, 25% were from Koya University, 1% was from Lebanese French University, 20 % were from Salahaddin University, 27% were from Soran University and 2% were from Tishk University. The relevant outcomes are displayed in Table (1).

Table 1. Frequency of samples by university

University Name	Frequency	Percent
Duhok University	25	25.0
Koya University	25	25.0
Lebanese French University	1	1.0
Salahaddin University	20	20.0
Soran University	27	27.0
Tishk University	2	2.0
Total	100	100

According to their gender, 35 of them were female and 65 males that is presented in table (4-2):

Table 2. Frequency of samples by gender

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Female	35	35
Male	65	65
Total	100	100

There were 44 % participants in the age group of 20–25-year-old, 34 of them in the age group of 26–30-year-old and 22 people in the age group of 31–35-year-old. The relevant outcomes are described in Table (3).

Table 3. Frequency of samples by age.

Age group	Frequency	Percent
20-25	44	44
26-30	34	34
31-35	22	22
Total	100	100

Moreover, there 44 participants were graduated in English Language and Literature, 42 were graduated in English language teaching, 10 were graduated in Linguistics and 4 were graduated in English Translation. The relevant results are described in Table 4:

Table 4. Frequency of samples by field.

Field of Study	Frequency	Percent
English Language and Literature	44	44
English language teaching	42	42
Linguistics	10	10
English Translation	4	4

Total	100	100
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The 98 participants were selected from governmental universities, 1 participant was selected from aided university and 1 participate was selected from private university. This is represented in Table (5).

Table 5. Frequency of samples by university type.

Type	Frequency	Percent
Governmental	98	44
Aided	1	42
Private	1	10
Total	100	100

How can students be inspired to improve their speaking skills when instructors provide an open conversation about various areas?

From the point of view of the people questioned in this research teaching today's students to speak more fluently is not a simple task. Teachers' creative abilities are severely restricted by time constraints and the need to complete specified items. Offering speaking extracurricular activities is one solution to this issue. One of the key components of communication that requires specific attention and teaching is speaking. The gathered data demonstrate that while designing English language speaking courses, educators should focus on identifying learners' requirements by speaking with both students and instructors' informants in order to get a balanced perspective. Since they provided a calm learning atmosphere free from fear of making errors, open discussion sessions were seen as an excellent way to improve students' speaking abilities. Students were given the chance to practice speaking in this learning environment, which also foster involvement, boost confidence, and prepare students for communication in the workplace. The project also gives other researchers the chance to investigate the potential national impact of Open Discussion Sessions, adding films and other interactive elements, allowing for varied gender and larger geographic groups. Here are some of the strategies that respondents have suggested to improve students' speaking abilities:

Listen as well as speak: Students are asked to listen to podcasts and discussions that have been recorded.

- Record the conversation practice: Students will probably make mistakes when speaking. But in order to learn from errors, people must be willing to make them. Students can learn more effectively if they record and play back the speaking they do with their discussion partner. Students may monitor their development and learn pronunciation in this method.
- Surround oneself with English: No matter where students reside, they may discover English-language meals, advertisements, books, movies, road signs, and other things.
- Practice with music and movies: Students have the option of watching movies in English or in their own language with readable English subtitles.
- Read aloud: Have the pupils attempt reading aloud. As a result of seeing and reading the words, students can hear how they are spoken and will remember them better.
- Speak with yourself: Students are asked to speak to themselves about daily chores that they are going to do.
- Improving pronunciation: Students are asked to use digital tools available on Internet pages or computers during the day to improve and enhance their pronunciation.
- Become familiar with English's natural flow: Every language has its own rhythm and flow. Understanding contractions is helpful while speaking English.
- Retell a story in English: Another technique to improve students speaking is to ask them to tell a story that they know in English.

Here are some direct quotes from the answers. One of the respondents mentioned the way of learning the mother tongue in childhood:

“When you're a kid, people point to things and tell you what they're called, and that's how you learn language. You should use the same strategy to study and improve your English.

Vocabulary is where it all starts. You may decide how many words you want to study each day."

Another one points to the impact of digital devices:

To help you learn pronunciation, there are digital programs that will say words aloud. Knowing the correct pronunciation is essential for communicating effectively, whether it is through YouTube channels or online dictionaries."

"Technology is available to help in language acquisition. You can practice speaking English anywhere with tools like Duolingo and Busuu, which connects you with native speakers.

Some have referred to the storytelling technique, for example one of the respondents expressed

Start with a straightforward story from your childhood or a fable. Then you may push yourself even farther by attempting to recount a narrative that someone else has told in English. This aids in evaluating your level of comprehension.

In reference to the flow and rhythm of each language it is explained that:

For instance, "I am" becomes "I'm" when two words are combined to make a single word. You should also be aware of which syllable to emphasize when speaking. Conversational practice and listening to native speakers are the only ways to achieve it.

In connection with the use of film and music, it is suggested that

Read the phrase aloud when you've finished. Play it back after that when the native speaker is speaking. To mimic the flow and rhythm as precisely as you can, try pausing in between. You may videotape yourself performing this if you'd like to hear how it sounds when a native speaker speaks.

Some suggested that students think for themselves with English:

You can assist teach yourself to think in English by first translating the ideas that are going through your brain. This probably won't come easily. As an alternative, you can keep a journal or thinking diary and write your entries in English.

Speak their ideas loudly:

Talking to yourself and hearing the words can help you get better, whether you decide to sing out or record yourself. You may read aloud as well.

One of the suggested techniques was that students put themselves in the English-speaking environment:

Events that feature public speaking, such as forums, conferences, and slam poetry competitions provide a suitable setting for listening to others talk. You could also submit an application to become a speaker. Public speaking may truly highlight your abilities if it's something less formal, like presenting your original work or telling a tale in front of a small group of friends.

There are language cafés all throughout the world. People can congregate here and engage in small-group language practice in their preferred languages.

Teacher Roles in Teaching Speaking

Respondents list several guidelines that educators must take into account when getting children ready to speak in English include:

1. Using games, situations where kids are actually trying to express themselves, and personalization to introduce and practice patterns in ways that seem relevant to the kids
2. Putting new patterns into practice alongside previously taught patterns to help pupils internalize them more quickly.

3. Giving the pupils lots of chances to speculate about how to apply the patterns flexibly in unusual circumstances.
4. Giving pupils the self-assurance to speak up in front of others by having them have individual conversations with other students and the class as a whole.
5. By giving the kids challenges to conquer and puzzles to solve, and making sure they are ultimately successful, teachers may help pupils develop their inner strength to deal with perplexing and unusual situations.

Children can learn new things by concentrating on the question formats of new patterns. Classify the teacher's tasks in teaching speaking in accordance with the other responses, as follows:

1. Prompter: Without interfering with the debate, teachers give students specific recommendations, then let them work things out on their own. They also give them chunks rather than words.
2. Attendee: The instructors take part in the debate by providing fresh material and ensuring that the students' involvement is maintained. The key message is that the instructor shouldn't dominate the dialogue.
3. Feedback provider: Teachers can provide some feedback by offering kindly and useful criticism as well as by informing the pupils of their performance. In addition, they should refrain from correcting pupils excessively because this might make them reluctant to continue the conversation.
4. Examiner: Teachers might record written examples of student language production or remember parts of it and then recite it to their pupils.
5. Viewer: The professors should watch the class speaking exercise and figure out why it falters.
6. Resource: Teachers must give their pupils certain resources to increase their oral proficiency.
7. Organizer: Teachers direct the activities in the classroom and involve the pupils.

Some respondents reported a misunderstanding of teachers' behavior:

I don't think many teachers consciously think about how they need to go from being instructors to becoming educators. When someone other than a regular college professor is chosen to teach a class, they frequently discover what works effectively in the classroom via experience and time. Audits of the classroom are likely to be conducted, and suggestions for continuous professional development will be made.

Others see the passage of time as an important factor that allows teachers to gain experience on their own.

The normal instructor will gradually develop into an educator as they look for tools to assist them become better teachers. However, I have dealt with several adjunct online professors who only depend on their subject-area knowledge and don't see the need to further their teaching careers.

Others have recommended using the new devices to transform through development of Instructional Practice tools, like:

You may learn new techniques, approaches, and practices through a variety of internet resources, books, workshops, webinars, and professional organizations. Additionally, social media platforms like LinkedIn and Twitter enable the sharing of information and ideas across an international community of educators.

Self-reflection is another tool you may use to assess your effectiveness. I've discovered that just after a class has ended is the ideal moment to evaluate my educational methods. At that point, I may evaluate my tactics and decide whether or not they were successful. Even though not all of the surveys that were submitted were good, analyzing the end-of-course student questionnaires may still shed light on my students' perspectives. When a student is extremely satisfied or extremely upset about the course, they are more likely to respond to

a survey. In any case, I may get knowledge about what my pupils have gone through in the classroom.

Also, we have some recommendations for transformation through the formation of Instructional Intellectual Abilities, like:

My experience with online faculty development has taught me that many instructors might benefit from this area of growth. However, unless it is discovered during classroom audits, it is frequently thought to be of low priority. Lackluster academic writing abilities will limit an educator's capacity to provide pupils thorough criticism.

While the researchers were reviewing the content of the questionnaires, there were some recommendations which evolved through acquiring subject-matter expertise, like:

Every educator has subject-specific knowledge they can use. The difficulty, though, is maintaining this knowledge as you work as a teacher for a while. Finding resources that enable you to study and learn about current ideas, research, and best practices in your chosen industry is the best advice I can give.

This is crucial to your teaching strategy since students can detect immediately if you seem knowledgeable and up to date or arrogant and out of date. Even using needed textbooks or materials does not guarantee that you are using the most up-to-date knowledge because many professions experience rapid knowledge evolution.

The last category of suggestions related to Improve Your Understanding of Adult Learning to Transform like:

Learning about the ideas, methods, and principles of adult learning is the final action or technique I can suggest. There are ideas you may explore, such as critical thinking, andragogy, self-directed learning, transformational learning, learning styles, motivation, and cognition, if you are unfamiliar with the fundamentals.

My idea is to look for and study online resources about higher education before deciding on a topic that interests you and doing more research on it. I've discovered that the more I learn about subjects I find interesting, the more I'm fostering an interest in continuing my professional growth. You'll probably discover that what you learn will improve all facets of your instructional practice and have a beneficial impact on your career as an educator. Making the decision to pursue this as a profession rather than a job is the first step in becoming an educator or another person who is deeply involved in the process of assisting pupils in learning. I have created a vision for how I want to participate in each class I teach, and I advise you to use the same approach. Creating teaching career objectives and connecting your classroom performance to them may be helpful to you. For instance, would you rather spend the extra time needed to establish supportive classroom environments or finish the essential facilitation tasks?

You may make a professional development plan to encourage your learning and improvement in each of the areas I have mentioned above after defining a vision and teaching goals. Although this tactic may demand time commitment, it is crucial to keep in mind that we always find time for the things we value most.

Being an educator means developing a passion for what you do and discovering ways to thrive for the benefit of your pupils, not just maintaining a focus on work duties. When you realize that educating kids is only one aspect of the learning process, and you make an effort to change who you are and how you behave while working and interacting with your students, you will become an engaging and transforming educator.

Regardless of your employment title, when you change your teaching or faculty function and become an educator, you also change the way your students learn. You provide them the essential component—meaningful instructor participation and engagement—necessary

for true learning to take place. More significantly, you personalize the educational process and support the child's developmental requirements. Students will leave your class changed in some way, having gained knowledge they may use in their academic endeavors, personal lives, and/or professional careers. You will change, and your pupils will too.

Barriers to Speaking English

The analysis of the presented answers in the field of barriers to speaking English shows that the raised barriers can be classified in six sections, which are mentioned below. Each of them is described briefly.

1. One of the main obstacles to speaking clearly, especially in English or any other foreign language, is a lack of confidence. Most presenters frequently struggle to articulate their views with confidence. They halt frequently when speaking, and their speech is incoherent. Their faces reflect their internal anxiety.
2. Lack of planning: An impromptu speech falls flat with the audience. Speakers frequently fail to take into account the meeting's topic, audience, location, or audiovisual equipment. Their lack of preparation causes their speech to fall short of expectations.
3. Poor ambiance: The size of the meeting space, appropriate lighting, seating arrangements, temperature, etc. are all factors that affect the ambiance or setting of a speech. A speech's success is greatly influenced by the environment in which it is delivered. It is impossible to deliver a speech that is effective if the atmospheric barrier is not broken.
4. Poor word choice: The fourth obstacle to speaking clearly is poor word choice. A speaker will not be understood by the audience if they are not cautious with word choice or if the words they choose are inappropriate for the context. He could also irritate them. His picture will be warped as a result.

In the following, we will selectively express some of the opinions that have been presented in this regard. Some respondents mentioned students' lack of self-confidence, such as:

Students usually lack the confidence necessary to speak and are terrified that they will make a mistake when they speak. Sometimes this stress causes their voice to tremble or them to sweat and blush.

Others have pointed to lack of coherence in the presentation of a topic, especially scientific topics:

When students are asked to comment on something, they are not prepared to say it or even do not have enough information to discuss a topic such as environmental protection, so they talk about it sparsely and this causes stress them and create a lack of planning in their speaking

The experience of some teachers shows that the way students sit in the classroom is influential, like:

Occasionally in free discourse classes I have experienced that the way students sit and the view of others towards the speaker has caused stress in the presenter or other students.

And some teachers see students' problems as more than just teaching a foreign language

Some students are poor speakers in terms of articulation, posture, or even body language, and have this problem in both their native language and English.

Factors that Contribute to the Existence of these Speaking Difficulties

In general, the respondents pointed to three very important factors in the occurrence of the mentioned problems related to students' speaking, the first of which is related to the education of students in the lower grades.

Strictness in the elementary levels of English language teaching, that is, exactly when the learner is faced with a large volume of misunderstandings, causes the learner to lose confidence in himself / herself, and at higher levels always have the stress of making a mistake.

The second factor that aggravates the problems of students in speaking is the lack of feeling the need to learn a second language, so that many students consider teaching a second language that started in school as a compulsion and only to get a good grade.

Forcing students to learn a foreign language without realizing its importance has made them bored.

The third influential factor that hinders the teaching of speaking is the difference between the grammar of the mother tongue and English. This is exacerbated when the student is presenting everyday phrases that are usually directly related to the culture of the individual.

Many students use their native language grammar when speaking and they translate it in their minds that this causes mistakes and the teacher has to explain how to pronounce the correct sentences from the mother tongue to English before any subject.

Perceptions of employing innovative approaches in teaching a speaking course among teachers and students

The results of this study showed that students are more eager to use new teaching methods due to the daily use of new technologies such as Internet and computers, while teachers are generally less IT literate due to their older age and therefore, they are less eager. Some of these ideas are presented below:

I am aware of the effectiveness of new technologies in improving student speaking, but I think it is better to do these methods outside the university because there is a need for devices that are difficult for us to use.

Due to my level of IT knowledge, the use of new technologies reduces my mastery of the class, because I must constantly pay attention to the type of presentation rather than what content that I present, but students welcome this and sometimes they have some suggestions in this regard.

What do undergraduate students think about EFL speaking instruction in universities?

Traditional teaching methods in universities have made students feel that the university is a place for study and written presentations only, and they continue to view speaking as an extra classroom activity, although they never reveal it. On the other hand, considering that the teaching and evaluation of speaking is significantly different from other courses, the general feeling of students is that speaking is just an administrative procedure and does not matter much, but other skills that are evaluated in writing are more important. One of comprehensive comments is as below:

In general, students find speaking very easy, and since questions are not pre-designed and does not have a written exam schedule, it is not taken very seriously by students.

DISCUSSION

There is a lack of confidence and students are afraid that they will make a blunder when they speak English. Students stated that they were unable to converse freely with their parents. This position is consistent with Tinkler (2002), who found that children sometimes lack confidence while speaking English in front of their parents, causing them to avoid school gatherings. Meanwhile, the data revealed that students are uncomfortable when speaking to people who are strangers or new to them and whom they have never met before. While speaking with the teacher or when the teacher corrects their blunders during a presentation or speech, they are also afraid and their hearts beat faster. According to Ohata (2005) and Woodrow (2008), giving oral presentations and performing in front of academics are two of the situations that cause the most anxiety. The results showed that when students were asked about something that caused stress, such as trembling and sweating, they did not even have enough information to equip themselves to deliver the correct message, and giving comments to students during speaking failed their goal. The results pointed out that students should speak to themselves loudly and pick up the correct pronunciation and intonation. And gradually progress from YouTube channels to online dictionaries, utilizing the skills and strengths of your communicative competency.

When compared to those who were exposed to the conventional technique, participants in EFL lessons have a more favorable perspective regarding speaking ability. The outcomes of this study

corroborate those of Sühendan & Bengü (2014) which found that students' perceptions regarding speaking abilities were enhanced by the CL strategy. Furthermore, the outcomes of the study suggest student shyness, with students feeling nervous in front of the teacher and audience when making a presentation or reading a lesson. As a result, pupils' speaking skills may suffer as a result of this problem. Furthermore, Crozier (2002) found that shy children and adults are quieter in social situations than their peers in another situation. Teaching EFL, especially speaking, is a significant duty. EFL teachers face difficulties and barriers while they carry out their instructional processes. The goal of this study was to look at the reasons behind Saudi EFL university teachers' difficulties in teaching the speaking skill, as well as possible remedies. The following are some of the hurdles that EFL university professors face when teaching the speaking skill, according to the study. The most significant barrier to Students switching to L1 during pair or group work was shown to be an effective method for teaching EFL speaking skills. Teaching the speaking skills took a lot of the instructors' time and was distressing.

RESULTS AND FINDING

In this study 100 individuals were participated that 25% respondents were from Duhok University, 25% were from Koya University, 1% was from Lebanese French University, 20 % were from Salahaddin University, 27% were from Soran University and 2% were from Tishk University. According to their gender, 35 of them were female and 65 males. There were 44 % participants in the age group of 20-25 year-old, 34 of them in the age group of 26-30 year-old and 22 people in the age group of 31-35 year-old. 44 participants were graduated in English Language and Literature, 42 were graduated in English language teaching, 10 were graduated in Linguistics and 4 were graduated in English Translation. 98 participants were selected from governmental universities, 1 participant was selected from aided university and 1 participate was selected from private university. According to participants' opinion new technologies especially English teaching applications play a strong roll in inspiring students to improve their speaking skills. Also, participants believe teachers can enhance the student's speaking skills by leading them to use computer biased application about English learning and at same time they teachers can inspire student by making a fun, energetic and creative atmosphere in class. In the field of barriers to speaking English results shows that the raised barriers can be classified in six sections including: lack of confidence, Lack of planning, Poor ambiance, Poor word choice, lack of coherence and the way students are seated.

CONCLUSIONS AND POLICY IMPLICATIONS

The goal of this paper was to figure out what leads EFL students to have weak speaking abilities. Lack of confidence, lack of preparation, terrible environment, incorrect word choice, poor gesture, and incorrect style are some of the prior flaws mentioned by the researcher in this work. Students with stronger drive and lower anxiety may communicate more readily and effectively, according to the study. As a result, pupils should be in a welcoming and cooperative setting that can assist them in overcoming their oral performance challenges. According to the study teachers should be aware of their students' interests and feelings, build up their learners' self-confidence, and use the best teaching strategies to keep them interested in the speaking activity.

Teachers should congratulate their pupils on their ability to communicate in English in order to foster a positive rapport with their students and to make them feel incredibly satisfied in the classroom; teachers should foster in them a great desire to study English in general and to speak English in particular. By offering speaking tasks that support their speaking and promoting their participation in speaking activities, teachers may provide their students more chances to practice speaking English. In order to prevent students from being afraid to make mistakes, teachers need also know when and how to rectify their students' mistakes. Teachers are recommended to employ this tactic consistently and profitably. the idea that EFL has a positive impact on students' development of positive speaking attitudes. The implications of this article is that EFL students at the University of the Kurdistan Region of Iraq have speaking challenges that can be solved by putting greater attention on this ability. Many concerns including instructors, instructional tactics, it is important to consider the curriculum, extracurricular activities, and

evaluation rules. Teachers need to learn how to teach speaking in a communicative way and how to combine it with other skills. Furthermore, instructors must be educated in many teaching practices that might help them limit their usage of L1 in their lessons. Students should have numerous opportunities to talk, and communication tasks should be included in the curriculum. Many researchers estimate that involving children in extracurricular activities might provide them more opportunity to use the language outside of the classroom, increasing their exposure to it overall.

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